

Positioning English in Cross-regional Developments in the Context of Globalization

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Abstract

This study examines the global implications of English within the context of globalization. In this regard, the influence of the language in native and non-native settings where it operates in capacities represented with varied nomenclatures (official language, national language, lingua franca, foreign language), are brought to the fore, in terms of the global status of English and the roles that the language performs within the scope, dynamics, prospects and constraints of globalization. Across the world, English demonstrates its communicative relevance in a wide range of discourse domains where proficiency in written and spoken English is an advantage to language users. To construe the world status of the English language in the of globalization, it is necessary to locate its development potential. Development is crucial in governance as every elected government aspires to improve the wellbeing of its citizens. Hinging on Orisawayi's (2005: 13-14) development parameters as a theoretical framework, this study concludes that given the global status and roles of English, the language facilitates development in all nations: English guarantees access to knowledge, fosters cross-regional communication, enables nations to cope with globalization-related phenomena and promotes regional development.

Keywords: *language, English, cross-regional development, globalization, Orisawayi's development parameters.*

1. Introduction

Globalization is a new multidimensional trend. Its grip on nations across the world is obvious in the scheme of things revolving around nationhood. It results in development-driven decisions in governance, including language-based development frameworks. The roles of English in such development frameworks accentuate its relevance in cross-border development. A study of the global status of English is immersed in the communicative potential of the language as fostered by different factors: its broad lexicon; adaptability in accommodating words from other origins; and formal properties (internal system). Within the context of globalization, the English language is viewed as a major driver of contemporary trends, practices and innovations across the world. By facilitating cross-facet information delivery and transmission of knowledge, English is a useful instrument to its users, particularly in this era of globalization when people rely heavily on information for social integration, capacity development and career pursuits in their immediate and remote environments. A chief means of human communication, language cannot be dislodged from societal phenomena. In the era of globalization, the world is viewed as a global village. The English language is one of the world's major languages. This study examines the position of English in the world stage, in terms of the way the language impinges on the development of individuals and nations across the world within the context of globalization.

2. Literature Review

This section of the paper reviews relevant literature.

2.1 Language

Scholars define language in different ways. What is fundamental is that language is a means of communication. Indeed, language is human heritage through which thoughts and ideas are conveyed from one person to another. Obiegbu Ifeyinwa (2014: 87) defines language as "a creation of man's social needs. Like all other living creatures, we depend on the air, water and earth around us, and in the same way, society depends upon language for its very existence. For

effective national development, language plays a central role, particularly in terms of such agents of development as literacy and communication. This is clearly understandable because it is through language that man has to plan ... Apart from the planning, man uses language to instruct and evaluate his programmes.”

2.2 Globalization

Hafsat Ahmad Abubakar (2014: 24) defines globalization as “a worldwide linkage entrepreneurship which centred on entrance to immediate global communication network where individuals can have access to information and movement globally.” As a norm, globalization affects status-quo in different countries, thereby dislodging socio-cultural and political order. Thus, it is a form of indispensable imposition on the human race in contemporary times. Kayode Omole (2016) cited in Ayodabo et al. (2016: 435) submits instructively on the term “globalization”:

Globalization refers to the universal adoption of social institutions. It is a process by which social institutions or policies become adopted on a world-wide scale ... ‘the age of globalization refers to that period of time when certain institutions or policies which may have been peculiar to or characterized certain geopolitical regions of the world or people become extended to or diplomatically imposed on other parts of the world.’ One of the institutions mostly affected by globalization is culture, characterized by the neglect of indigenous languages by African youths and elite. There are many factors responsible for this. Among them are the official status of English and French in many African countries, the founding of many international schools or educational institutions that promote or emphasize the learning of these international languages, massive onslaught of foreign movies and magazines and the elitist aspirations of parents who tend to make English or French the first language of their authentic African children. Given all these social circumstances, Africa’s indigenous languages are being gradually disowned by their speakers.

Besides culture, a wide range of societal phenomena are captured by globalization, even though some aspects of globalization tend to be more overriding than others, e.g. science and technology. David Crystal (1983: 10) reports globalization-related trends on nations:

... economic developments beginning to operate on a global scale supported by the new communication technologies – telegraph, telephone, radio – and fostering the emergence of massive multinational organizations. The growth of competitive industry and business brought an explosion of international marketing and advertising. The power of the press reached unprecedented levels soon to be surpassed by the broadcasting media, with the ability to cross national boundaries with electromagnetic ease. Technology chiefly in the form of movies and records, fuelled new mass entertainment industries which had a worldwide impact. The drive to make progress in science and technology fostered an international intellectual research environment which gave scholarship and further education a high profile.

Commenting further on globalization, Steger (2019: 7-8) posits that globalization is “the interconnections of global economic, political, cultural and environmental processes that continually transform present conditions.” For Nataliya Todorova and Anna Todorova 2018: 333), “... globalization has no precise definition, but numerous meanings and interpretations in different areas such as cultural studies, economics, environment or politics. While some students consider globalization as a social process that makes the currently existing borders irrelevant, others stress the world-unifying, homogenizing power of this process. This term generalized, globalization, globalization (which obviously comes from the word ‘globe’) is the ‘big idea’ of 20th century, which contains the process of international integration arising from the exchange of worldwide views, products, products, ideas, and other aspects of culture and life.” A major feature of globalization is interdependency in various spheres of society, leading to sharing of knowledge, information, technology, security architecture, crisis management strategies, managerial skills, etc. These trends are particularly beneficial to Third World countries with low literacy level, high poverty rate, health challenges and security threats.

2.3 English as a Global Language

As a global language, English impinges on the growth of world economy, politics, education, science and technology directly and indirectly. The language plays a foundational role in the development trends of the present world. While some scholars prefer to label the English language as an “international language”, there are those who refer to it as a “global language”. These two labels accentuate the pride of place of the language in the world, that has become a global village, ravished by the fall-outs of globalization. Phillipson (2008: 4) cited in Poggensee Anna (2016) contends that “‘global English’ is an appropriate term because English is widely accepted in the global linguistic market and ... English is becoming the defiant language of international communication in an increasing number of countries worldwide. On the other hand, Ammon (2010: 11) uses the terms ‘international language’ or ‘world language’ to describe the English language because of its function as a language of international communication. He believes that ‘the more international the language or the higher its international standing, the more justified its claim to the status of a world language.’”

Rohmah Zuliatu (2005: 107) provides insight on the notion “global language”:

About fifty years ago the notion of English as a true global language was merely a theoretical prediction which is still diffuse and vague. However, realities have created it as a real world language at the present time. People in every part of the world feel its urgent role in their life: for academic purposes, for business goals, and for other purposes. English is spoken by people throughout the world as their first language, second language and foreign language. Indeed, English is now a world language.

English as a world language is not merely an international language. The notion of international language can be understood as a language which is used in any international communication which involves people from two or more countries. Japanese is an international language, but it is not a global language ...

It is logical to view the global status of the English language in relation to the continued world-power position of its natives: America (in particular) and Britain who have major stakes in world economy, military, science and technology. In this regard, David Crystal (ibid.) rightly states that “given that the USA has come to be dominant element in so many of the domains ..., the future status of English must be bound up to some extent with the future of that country. So much of the power which has fuelled the growth of the English language during the twentieth century has stemmed from America. ... the country contains nearly four times as many mother-tongue speakers of English as any other nation. It has been more involved in international developments in twentieth-century technology than any other nation. It is in control of the new industry (that is, electronic) revolution. And it exercises a greater influence on the way English is developing worldwide than any other regional variety – often, of course, to the discomfiture of people in the UK, Australia, New Zealand, Canada and South Africa who regularly express worries in their national presses about the onslaught of ‘Americanisms’.” The spread of speakers of English across the world is a proof of its imperial feat and relevance in the scheme of things that globalization offers to the human race in contemporary times. Akin Odebunmi (2017: 21) reports that “in his theory of linguistic imperialism, Phillipson (1992) (re-) groups global English speakers into core English speaking countries, comprising Britain, the United States, Canada, Australia and New Zealand; and ‘periphery English-speaking countries’, where English serves as a second language (for example, Nigeria, Ghana, India and Singapore) or an international language (for example, China, Indonesia and Japan). The groups relate unequally with respect to structural and systemic power in that the Western Anglophone group wields political and socio-economic power against the former colonial communities found in the peripheries. This hegemony is further sustained by ‘English linguistic imperialism’, defined as ‘the dominance of English’ ... asserted and maintained by the establishment and continuous reconstruction of structural and cultural inequalities between English and other languages.” The global status of English is established in the literature with adequate statistical claims. One of such is Nataliya Todorova and Anna Todorova (ibid: 336) report on the British Council’s statistics:

- English has official or special status in at least 75 countries, with a total population of more than two billion;
- one out of four of the world’s population speak English to some level of competence; demand from the other three quarters is increasing;
- more than two thirds of the world’s scientists read in English;
- three quarters of the world’s mail are written in English;
- 80 per cent of the world’s electronically stored information is in English.

3. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical anchorage of this study is Orisawayi’s (ibid) development parameters. According to Orisawayi’s (ibid: 13-14) parameters for ascertaining development are as follows:

1. Intellectual and mental expansion for the individual person in society;
2. a stable polity with a strong sense of commitment to nationalism/nationhood among the people;
3. economic development, progress and equitable distribution of national wealth;
4. socio-political integration of the constituent units that make up the nation;
5. scientific and technological progress and its application to the improvement of the quality of life of the people;
6. efficient and functional educational output at all levels;
7. widely recognized, accepted and practiced democratic structures and systems;
8. highly enlightened citizenry with 80%-90% achieved level of functional literacy among the people and highly sharpened awareness of individual and collective fundamental rights, with freedom of speech and association;
9. stable employment for all citizens in private and public sectors of the economy;
10. a highly recognized and respectable network of understanding and positive relations among the constituent units and with other nations of the world;
11. a highly developed network of communication and transport system; and
12. a high sense of motivation among the citizenry towards the achievement of all the parameters of development indices.

The above theoretical framework is suitable for the thrust of this study because it reveals the aspects of nationhood where the positive effects of the English language can be felt if the language is deployed by nations across the world, to cope with evolved and evolving globalization trends and practices.

4. English in Cross-regional Development in the Context of Globalization

In this section of the implications of English in cross-regional development are examined within the context of globalization.

4.1 Cross-facet Development

Ifeyinwa Obiegbu (2014 :87-88) submits that “language generally plays a very important role in national development because it helps to promote unity, understanding and a sense of belonging among the various members of the different ethnic and social groups that constitute a nation.” In addition, Akaegbobi Oby et al. (2001: 94) cites that “... language is the tool used to bring realities into existence. The human achievements are said to be products of intensive thinking and reflections ... Indeed, language is so central to thinking or thought that no thought is possible where language is absent ... our understanding of national development rests on language, without whose intervention, the term, national development will be an empty sound signifying nothing.” By functioning as a national language in different countries, the English language facilitates nation-building in discrete ways. This view corroborates Fasold (1984: 77) who submits:

- 1) the emblem of national oneness and identity;
- 2) widely used for some everyday purposes;
- 3) widely and fluently spoken within the country;
- 4) the major candidate for such a role, since there is no equally qualified alternative language within the country;
- 5) acceptable as a symbol of authenticity; and
- 6) having a link with the glorious past.

Giving elaborate perspective on the term “national language”, Holmes Janet (2008: 100-101) submits:

In sociolinguistics the distinction between a national language and an official language is generally made along the affective-referential dimension, or more precisely in this context, the ideological-instrumental dimension. A national language is the language of a political, cultural and social unit. It is generally developed and used as a symbol of national unity. Its functions are to identify the nation and unite its people. An official language, by contrast, is simply a language which may be used for government business. Its function is primarily utilitarian rather than symbolic. It is possible, of course, for one language to serve both functions. Not surprisingly, governments do not always recognise the distinctions made by sociolinguists. They use the terms ‘official’ and ‘national’ to suit their political ends ... Many countries make no distinction between a national language and an official language. In countries which regard themselves as monolingual nations, the same language serves both purposes. In multilingual communities, however, all kinds of permutations have been used in order to satisfy both political and social goals on the one hand, and more practical and utilitarian needs on the other. In multilingual countries, the government often declares a particular language to be the national language for political reasons. The declaration may be a step in the process of asserting the nationhood of a newly independent or established nation, for instance, as in the case of Swahili in Tanzania, Hebrew in Israel, Malay in Malaysia, and Indonesian in Indonesia. Where this national language cannot serve all the internal and external functions of government business, however, it has been necessary to identify one or more official languages as well. So French is an official language in many countries, such as the Ivory Coast and Chad, where French was previously a colonial power and Arabic is an official language in Israel alongside Hebrew.

The identification of official languages may also be necessary when the choice of national language is problematic. In multilingual India, for example, attempts to give Hindisole status as the national language have not succeeded. Fourteen regional Indian languages are recognised as official languages alongside English and Hindi for the country as a whole, and in addition different states each have their own official languages. Talegu, for instance, is the official language of the state of Andhrap Pradesh. Some multilingual countries have nominated more than one national language.

Some countries experience repeated failures in achieving set development goals. This is partly because an effective linguistic approach to cross-facet national development is not deployed. Such an approach fosters national cohesion which translates into nation-building. Through a language with global vitality (like the English language), governance culminates into the overall wellbeing of the populace. This is particularly so in this era of globalization when the use of English for national identity and cohesion is non-negotiable. According to Chukwudi R. O. and Oboko U. (2021: 26), nation-building is “... the aim of unifying the people within the state, in order to engender political, economic and socio-cultural viability and stability of the state ...” A linguistic approach to nation-building is anchored by the belief that language is fundamental to the smooth running of a nation (nationism). As a viable tool in governance, language cannot be ignored in nation-building. Ushuple Lucy Mishina and Iskandar Iskandar (2019: 59) rightly notes that “language has started to be treated as a powerful political instrument ... language can be used in many ways; one of them is in specific purpose areas such as social or cultural communication, government decisions, political debate, media which could foster National Development ...”

4.2 Regional and Cross-border Communication

English facilitates regional and cross-border communication. It is a language of wider communication (LWC). Ushuple Lucy M. and Iskandar I. (ibid: 63) avers that “as a language of wider communication (LWC), English is used for phatic communion, ceremonial purpose, an instrument of keeping records, information dissemination, self-expression and embodiment of thought among the various linguistic groups in Nigeria. The common linguistic basis that constitutes a requisite for the existence of any nation is provided by English. So, with English as the common tongue to all the ethnic groups, the collective sentiment of belonging together despite the individual or ethnic differences is forged. Related to the discussion is the fact that Nigerian Nationalism or collective identity is stamped on national institutions through the medium of English.” Thus, English is very useful to whoever writes or speaks proficiently in it. Nataliya Todorova and Anna Todorova (ibid: 336) reports that “according to the 2004 Euro barometer survey, 75 per cent of Europeans supported the idea that English is the most useful language to learn, while 69 per cent were confident that every EU citizen should speak English. English leads the world both in terms of total speakers as well as being the most commonly studied foreign language.

The leading role of English as a common medium for international communication is also supported by the following commonly recognized facts.”

4.3 Access to Knowledge

The English language is instrumental in accessing knowledge in different domains of society including formal instructional settings (schools). Clement Gowon Omachonu, Joseph Abuh and Habiba Oma Alhassan (2017: 167) submit that “the modern goal of English language teaching should be how to equip learners with the knowledge and critical awareness of how globalization defines and positions their use of the language. Consequently, teachers of English as a second language need to adopt methodologies that will envision English language teaching within the context of globalization.” In promoting English studies for nation-building, learners are expected to achieve appreciable mastery of discrete skills that are productive for national development. Nataliya Todorova and Anna Todorova (ibid: 326) submit that “multinational companies require a certain degree of English proficiency from potential employees. It means that more and more people nowadays learn English in order to get the best possible professional training and employment opportunities with top companies.” Adeniran, cited in Ayodabo (2013: 82) lists three degrees of competence in language:

- Minimal Competence
Speakers are characterized by a single speech habit in a single social sphere without any shifting of repertoire or code (restricted).
- Average Competence
Speakers have a command of a set of speech habits which is neither large nor small; they use this in a limited range of different social spheres, and shift their verbal repertoire accordingly (flexible).
- Maximum Competence
Speakers have versatile speech habits in many social spheres, and shift their verbal repertoire with ease (versatile).

In former British colonies where English is lingua franca, the education system promote the teaching and learning of English for sustainable growth and development. Communication skills are taught and literacy in the language increases worldwide. Through the efforts of primary, secondary and tertiary institutions in different countries, intercultural communication and mutual intelligibility between regional English(es) and Standard British English (SBE) are enhanced. English has rich vocabulary stock; thus, it is suitable as medium of instruction in schools. Its vocabulary stock captures terms and concepts of various disciplines as well as research phenomena of innumerable proportion.

The wide scope of the English vocabulary is partly informed by its robust capacity to accommodate words from other non-English origins: French words, Arabic words, Latin words, etc. David Crystal (ibid: 146) submits:

Most adaptation in a new English relates to vocabulary, in the form of new words (borrowings – from several hundred language sources, in such areas as Nigeria), word-formations, word-meanings, collocations and idiomatic phrases. There are many cultural domains likely to motivate new words, as speakers find themselves adapting the language to meet fresh communicative needs. A country’s biogeographical uniqueness will generate potentially large numbers of words for animals, fish, birds, insects, plants, trees, rocks, rivers and so on – as well as the issues to do with land management and interpretation which is an especially important feature of the lifestyle of many indigenous peoples. There will be words for foodstuffs, drinks, medicines, drugs, and the practices associated with eating ... The country’s mythology and religion, and practices in astronomy and astrology, will bring forth new names for personalities, beliefs and rituals. The country’s oral and perhaps written literature will give rise to distinctive names in sagas, poems, oratory and folktales. There will be a body of local laws and customs, with their own terminology. The culture will have its own technology with its own terms – such as for vehicles, house – buildings, weapons, clothing, ornaments and musical instruments. The whole world of leisure and the arts will have a linguistic dimension – names of dances, musical styles, games,

sports – as will distinctiveness in body appearance (such as hair styles, tattoos, decoration). Virtually any aspect of social structure can generate complex naming systems – local government, family relationships, clubs and societies, and so on ... So, when a community adopts a new language, and starts to use it in relation to all areas of life, there is inevitably going to be a great deal of lexical creation.

In this era of globalization when innovations and research evolve massively, a global language accommodates the communicative exigencies of transmitting knowledge. In this sense, the English language can be construed as the world's lingua franca. Laxman Jnawali (2024: 15-16) asserts that “this language has worked as a bridge among various bilingual and multilingual communities where English language has been used as second or foreign language ... The language has been very popular in social media as well. People from multilingual communities are actively involved in learning English as their second and foreign language. People are learning IELTS, TOEFL, PTE, GRE and many others in order to go to the foreign countries for various purposes. According to David Crystal (ibid: 112), “since the 1960s, English has become the normal medium of instruction in higher education for many countries – and is increasingly used in several where the language has no official status ... The English language teaching (ELT) business has become one of the major growth industries around the world in the past half-century. However, its relevance to the growth of English as a world language goes back much further. Indeed, people who engage in international business and commerce have also been taking interest in English language.”

Worker-productivity is heavily reliant on language. Organisational cohesion can only be achieved through a conventional means of communication: language. In this era of globalization, a world language is the ideal tool for information transmission. By enhancing the contribution of workers in all facets of life, the English language contributes significantly to the wellbeing of the human race. Zuliatu Rohmah (ibid: 121) notes that “language plays a crucial role in the improvement of a person. It helps the individual have a sense of self-worth, wider career possibilities, greater ease, when travelling, broader cultural horizons, and enriched education ... Proficiency in the knowledge of English helps us to access increased industrialization. Good command of English also equips an individual to be in a position of honour such as political positions as well as appointments into several services ...” Omodiaogbe cited in Eyisi (2007:18) asserts that “so long as most textbooks are written in English and so long as the language remains an international one and a veritable gateway to the understanding and mastering of science and technology, it will continue to be the *premius inter pares* if not the *numero uno*.”

English remains a facilitator of development of contemporary nations because of its literacy-promotion potential across the world. Ifeyinwa Obiegbu (ibid: 81) submits that “the importance of English programme in the context of a developing nation like Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized. This is because there are two dominant areas in which it is very necessary for national development; Literacy and Communication. Similarly, there are three aspects of literacy which inevitably link it with socio-economic development, such as the correlation between illiteracy and poverty, social transformation as well as economic growth. To achieve socio-economic development, Nigeria needs a common language. that will offer a hitch-free access and ensure mass participation in national development. The English language therefore serves this all important purpose.”

4.4 Coping with Globalization

Globalization trends pose challenges to nations. In such challenges, the communicative potency of the English language is heavily relied upon. For example, as a global language, English is used to mobilize the world in the advent of a pandemic as it was during the outbreak of Covid-19. Without a common means of communication with global spread, it would have been difficult, if not impossible, to spur the world for a common action against the pandemic. During the pandemic, several meetings were held, and in such meetings, English was the major means of communication even though there were instances of interpretations and translations in other languages. Several enlightenment sessions were held across the world using English as a means of communication: in media briefings, English was the means of communication; in the advertisements that were made to educate and sensitize people on curbing Covid-19, English was the means of communication; world leaders held political meetings using English as a means of communication; and there were associational meetings of medics and other health workers in which English was used as a linguistic code for deliberations. Thus, the language was deployed for solidarity and public mobilization. Wardhaugh R. and Janet M. Fuller (2015: 9) comment on the mobilization and solidarity function of language by asserting that “solidarity refers to the motivations which cause individuals to act together and to fulfill a common bond which influences their social actions. Thus the concept of solidarity is intertwined with both identity formation and group formation.” Being a successful language in regions where it functions in one capacity or the other, English enables nations to cope with world affairs of enormous proportions. In this era of globalization, nations are generally in dire need of national development. In such a situation, a global language like the English language becomes indispensable. Obasi (1987) defines “national development” as “the progressive transformation of the economic, social and political structures of a society from relatively less complex, less efficient and less desirable forms to relatively more complex, more efficient and more desirable forms.” In addition, Akaegbobi, Oby et al. (ibid: 77) comments instructively on the term “national development”:

The imperatives of national development stems from the recognition that besides what the whole world has professed to achieve, each nation has to devise home grown mechanism to improve the quantity and quality of lives of their citizens. It is also built on the understanding that all countries of the world do not share the same needs. In national development each country focuses on what it considers important in the improvement of lives of its citizens ... national development is not a destination. Thus, there is no point which a country will reach and it will conclude that it has attained national development. We rather say that national development is a process, a continuous process

David Crystal (ibid) succinctly captures ways in which English empowers nations to cope with globalization-related trends:

The socio-cultural explanation looks at the way people all over the world, in many walks of life, have come to depend on English for their economic and social well-being. The language has penetrated deeply into the international domains of political life, business, safety communication, entertainment, the media and education. The convenience of having a global lingua franca available to serve global human relations and needs has come to be appreciated by millions. Several domains ... have come to be totally dependent on it – the computer software industry being a prime example. A language’s future seems assured when so many organizations come to have a vested interested in it.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Use of language in society is domain-specific. In different countries, English language is used in schools, churches, mosques, hospitals, markets, offices, banks, parliaments, etc. David Crystal (ibid: 109) submits that “the language plays an official or working role in the proceedings of most other major international political gatherings, in all parts of the world. Examples include the Association of South-East Asian Nations, the Commonwealth, the Council of Europe, the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization.” In contemporary times, linguistic approaches to national development is gaining momentum, because communication, which is conveyed via language, is a major tool for national and cross-border development. The global status of English which positions it for cross-regional roles in the wake of globalization is a major reason why nations accept and manage the dynamics of making the language co-exist with other languages in such nations. Individuals have improved their productive capacity due to their proficiency in English. Thus, the language translates into individualistic economic empowerment in nations where it is used as a foreign language, second language, lingua franca. Across the world, language policy frameworks that foster the co-existence of English with indigenous languages give English more global relevance and international dominance in the era of globalization.

Desire for bilingual competence is becoming typical of contemporary world, as triggered by the link between globalization and language. Goethals (2002) succinctly captures the implications of intercultural communication by asserting that “language is human interaction. It is active and dynamic. It shapes: it deconstructs the world through fiction, myth and narration.” In a similar vein, Denise Lussier (2007: 320) posits that “‘interacting’ is perceived as the development of intercultural skills to emerge from learning and experiences in a target language and cultural environment. It goes beyond discourse, sociolinguistic and discourse competence per se. Learners are able to take into account other contexts of ways of living, traditions, behaviours, customs and values when interacting socially with people from other cultures. It even brings the learner to meta-analysis of language which leads to a reflective stage of discourse and the capacity for intercultural argumentation. Learners become able to decode messages which can carry different interpretations. They are able to negotiate conflict and situations of misunderstandings.” Population growth in all nations triggered by job-seeking and carrer pursuits results in unprecedented global migration with new world order in the scheme of things, language inclusive. David Crystal (ibid: 18) notes that “these days, there are clear signs of growing awareness, within English-speaking communities of the need to break away from the traditional monolingual bias. In economically hard-pressed times, success in boosting exports and attracting foreign investment can depend on subtle factors, and sensitivity to the language spoken by a country’s potential foreign partners is known to be particularly influential ... there are signs of a growing respect for other cultures, and a greater readiness to engage in language learning. Language attitudes are changing all the time, and more and more people are discovering, to their great delight, that they are not at all bad at picking up a foreign language.” Literacy in a global language in the era of globalization implies improved work-pace productivity in all nations, and this is because development is the product of information delivery and management, through the instrumentality of language.

This study concludes that all nations benefit in the developmental dividends that English offers in the era of globalization, because the language gives such nations access to knowledge, communication and the necessary resources to cope with the challenges of globalization.

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